

PHYCO
DATABASE

Booklet

Morphological Characteristics of
Coelastrum cambricum from the Peat
Water, Palangka Raya, Indonesia

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**Phyco Data Base Booklet: Morphological Characteristics of
Coelastrum cambricum from the Peat Water, Palangka Raya,
Indonesia**

Based on the research:

Adam, C., & Haryono, A. 2022. Morphological Study of *Coelastrum cambricum* from the Peat Water of Palangka Raya, Indonesia. NST Proceeding: BASC Series Volume 2022 DOI:

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The data is also published online and can be accessed publicly at

<https://phycodatabase.weebly.com/>:

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Introduction

This booklet is an e-book version of the Phyco Data Base describing the general characteristics of *Coelastrum cambricum* based on the results of research conducted by [Adam & Haryono \(2022\)](#) entitled:

Morphological Study of Coelastrum cambricum from the Peat Water of Palangka Raya, Indonesia.

Taxonomic Hierarchy of *Coelastrum cambricum*

Phylum: Charophyte

Class: Chlorophyceae

Order: Sphaeropleales

Family: Scenedesmaceae

Genus: *Coelastrum*

Species: ***C. cambricum* W. Archer 1868**

Coelastrum cambricum
Source: [Adam & Haryono \(2022\)](#)

Habitat Characteristics

Coelastrum cambricum was identified from the water samples collected from peat water in Palangka Raya, Indonesia. The peat water has a brownish color and looks fairly clear like brewed tea that allows enough sunlight to penetrate into it (Adam & Haryono, 2022). The depth ranges from 30-50 cm and there is a lot of leaf litter on the surface because on the sides of the trench there are lots of *Acacia* trees that are shedding their leaves. Measurements of physicochemical parameters show that peat water has a temperature (T) of 31.4°C, a potential of Hydrogen (pH) 5, and total dissolved solids (TDS) of 13ppm (Adam & Haryono, 2022).

Figure 1. Peat Water (Palangka Raya, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia).
Image source: Adam & Haryono (2022)

The high levels of acidity and organic material in peat water depend on its region and vegetation types ([Huling et al., 2001](#)). The vegetation along the peat water ditch in this study consisted of *Acacia* trees shedding their leaves and grass growing into the peat water. This state of vegetation contributes to most of the organic matter in the peat water at the study site to support the growth of microalgae in it including *C. cambricum* ([Adam & Haryono, 2022](#)).

Morphological Characteristics

Coelastrum cambricum forms a spherical coenobium consisting of 4-32 cells and appears green in color and it is observed that coenobium groups form larger colonies consisting of 4 to 24 coenobia (Figure 2). The diameter of coenobia ranges from 40-62 μm (Adam & Haryono, 2022).

Figure 2. *Coelastrum cambricum*: (A) Coenobia; and (B) Larger colonies consisting of 4-24 coenobia. Image source: Adam & Haryono (2022)

C. cambricum cells are joined together forming a coenobium by a certain gelatinous substance that binds the cells of a coenobium appears colorless but clearly visible at 400 \times magnification (Adam & Haryono, 2022). The gelatinous substance is composed of collagen in the form of protein-type cellulose fibrils and has various roles in the survival of microalgae. The main function of gelatinous substance is to regulate the locomotion of cells, retain colonies and plays an

intermediate role in symbiotic association for cell-cell communication (Watanabe et al., 2006). Lange (1976) stated that the level of substance thickness in the cell sheath is associated with the content of essential nutrients in the environment surrounding the microalgae. The gelatinous sheath will remain thick if organic matter as an important nutrient is available because it is not attacked by bacteria associated with algae. These bacteria tend to attack the gelatinous layer on the microalgae cell envelope if there is no other organic material that can be assimilated (Lange, 1976).

Figure 3. Certain gelatinous substance that binds the cells of the coenobium together. *Image source: Adam & Haryono (2022)*

Cells are spherical range between 6-21 μ m in diameter with large blunt rounded processes toward the outer face of the external cells and covered with a delicate gelatinous sheath (Adam & Haryono, 2022). The intercellular space formed in the coenobium is triangular in shape and it is also observed that some are slightly narrow (Adam & Haryono, 2022). Figure 4 shows a close-up view of each cell in a different position with the shape of the intercellular space.

Figure 4. Cell morphology of *C. cambricum* at different positions in a coenobium. Image source: Adam & Haryono (2022)

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